

Patterns of Bottom Sediment Contamination in Parts of River Ogun Lagos, Nigeria¹Akoteyon, I. S. and ²Kodja, D. J.

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ABSTRACT: The study analyzed the patterns of bottom sediment contamination in parts of River Ogun Lagos, Nigeria. Samples were randomly collected from ten locations and were analyzed for ten heavy metals using the digestion and atomic absorption spectrophotometer technique. Data were analyzed using descriptive and environmental indicators. The result shows that the concentrations of Pb, Cd, As, Cu and Hg exceeded the global background values of bottom sediment in the study area. The contamination factors of Pb, As, Cd and Hg indicate very high contamination. All the locations indicate pollution based on the PLI value. Half of the locations indicate very severe contamination based on the pollution contamination index with contributions from Pb, Cd, As, Cu and Hg. The I-geo of Cr, Ni, As and Cu indicate low contamination while only 40 and 30% of the locations are indicative of heavy and extremely contamination based on the I-geo of Mn and Cd respectively. The study concluded that Ogudu is the worst site based on heavy metal concentrations, Cf, and PLI. The study provides useful baseline information on heavy metal concentrations and ecological risk of bottom sediments contamination in the study area. Proper monitoring and regulation of heavy metal in the aquatic environment for policy decisions with greater priority at Ogudu due to its worst quality status were proffered.

Keywords: Bottom sediment, Contamination, Environmental indices, River Ogun

INTRODUCTION

Sediments are essential elements of aquatic ecosystems because they support both autotrophic and heterotrophic organisms (MacDonald, *et al.* 2003). However, the current uncontrolled urbanization, industrial and agricultural activities pose a significant environmental challenge to the sediment quality of Rivers in developing countries (Moore, *et al.* 2009). The accumulation of heavy metals from diverse sources such as point and diffuse origin into bottom sediment have a significant influence on the aquatic life and consequently its quality deterioration. The problem of heavy metal contamination in the aquatic environment constitutes a major concern due to their persistent nature in the environment and the adverse effects on living organisms and humans through the food chains (Sabo, *et al.* 2013).

Most of the impacts of sediment contamination on the ecosystem are associated with contaminants that have direct effects on benthic communities and also on the upper trophic levels through food chain contamination (Burton, 2002). Studies have shown that metals can either be adsorbed onto suspended particles or in dissolved forms through runoff into water bodies (Yurkovskis & Poikāne, 2008; Remeikaitė-Nikienė, *et al.* 2018). Some heavy metals such as cadmium, lead and mercury can come through atmospheric deposition (Remeikaitė-Nikienė *et al.*, 2018). Similarly, within the aquatic environment, some metals can accumulate in bottom sediments with other components like organic matter, iron-manganese hydroxides etc. (Dang, *et al.* 2015). Despite the importance of some of these metals e.g. Zn and Cu, which are considered an essential element for life, others such as Pb, Cd are highly deleterious to living organisms even at low

concentrations (Jakimska, *et al.* 2011). Bottom sediment contamination resulting from heavy metals constitute great concern due to their toxicity, persistence, and bioaccumulation in the aquatic environment and their negative impacts on living organisms (Nemati, *et al.* 2011; Ravisankar, *et al.* 2015).

Sediment quality assessment serves as a useful tool for examining the health quality status of the aquatic ecosystem for environmental pollution monitoring, management and abatement of ecological risk (Aladesanmi, *et al.* 2016). Sediment quality assessment also provides historical evidence of an anthropogenic effect on the aquatic environment (Al-Najjar, 2011; Al-Mur, *et al.* 2017). The major sediment quality assessment methods include the index of geo-accumulation (I-geo), pollution load index (PLI), contamination factor (Cf), enrichment factor (EF), and potential contamination index (PCI) (Adel, *et al.* 2011). These techniques are geared towards providing information on the overall level of heavy metal contamination in sediments for policy decisions (Burton, 2002; Priju & Narayana, 2006; Adel, *et al.* 2011).

The study, therefore, seeks to analyze the patterns of bottom sediment contamination in parts of River Ogun, Lagos, Nigeria using environmental indicators. The study is significant because it will provide baseline information on river sediment quality to proffer efficient environmental monitoring and regulation of potential ecological risks for sustainable environmental management. The study will also assist policymakers in planning, and monitoring points and diffused pollutants in a sustainable manner.

Study Area

The study area lies on Long 3⁰ 22' 30''E and 3⁰ 28' 30'' E to Lat 6⁰ 34' 00'' N and 6⁰ 39' 00'' N. River Ogun is one of the major rivers in southwestern Nigeria. The climate is typical of Tropical wet and dry seasons according to Koppen's classification (Aderogba, 2012). The dry season spans from November to April, while the wet season is experienced from April through October with a cessation in mid-August (Aderogba, 2012). The annual average rainfall is 1,532mm, with an annual mean temperature of about 27⁰C. The vegetation is dominated by tropical swamp forests, consisting of freshwaters/mangrove swamp forests and dry lowland rain forests (FEPA, 1997).

The watershed has low relief with the gradient in the North-south direction (Adeosun, *et al.* 2014). The river takes its source from Igaran hills at an elevation of about 540 m above sea level and flows directly southward over a distance of 480 km before it discharges into the Lagos Lagoon (Adeosun, *et al.* 2014). The river has an approximate total area of 22.4 km² and flows through Oyo, Ogun and Lagos states before it finally discharges into the Lagoon (Oketola, *et al.* 2006; Osunkiyesi, 2012). The major tributaries of the river are Ofiki River and Opeki River (Adeosun, *et al.* 2014). The river is used for agriculture, transportation, domestic and industrial purposes (Oketola, *et al.* 2006). The river has continued to suffer degradation due to the release of effluent from various sources such as breweries, slaughterhouses, dyeing industries, tanneries and domestic wastewater (Oketola, *et al.* 2006).

Figure 1: Study area

Methodology

Sample collection and preparation

Single bottom sediment samples were collected from 10 randomly selected locations on River Ogun in parts of Lagos, Nigeria in December 2019. The sediment quality assessment was carried out based on the concern of environmental degradation resulting from industries, agricultural activities etc. Sediment samples were collected inside a polythene bag with the aid of a soil auger and stored in an ice chest before being transferred to TETRA ‘A’ analytical and diagnostic laboratory, Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria for analysis. The bottom sediment samples were poured into porcelain crucibles and were oven-dried at about 80°C for 3hours. Thereafter, 2.0g of the sediment samples were measured using the electronic balance model M 10001 digital machine. The sediments were crushed with the aid of pestle and mortar and were sieved through 2mm mesh.

The samples were poured into a 100 ml volumetric flask and digested with 15.0 ml of HNO₃ and HCl acid in the ratio of 1:3 (aqua-regia). The samples were analyzed for ten heavy metals namely; Manganese (Mn), Nickel (Ni), Lead (Pb), Zinc (Zn), Arsenic (As) Cobalt (Co), Chromium (Cr), Copper (Cu), Cadmium (Cd) and Mercury (Hg) using digestion and atomic absorption spectrophotometer with the aid of AAS VGB 210 System model. The analysis was carried out following the quality assurance and control (QA/QC) protocol prescribed by the Standard Organisation of Nigeria (SON) for sediment reference materials. The coordinate of the sample locations was recorded using the Global Positioning System (GPS) Garmin map, 76CSX model and the patterns of the sediment quality was mapped with the aid of ArcMap 10.3.1 version.

Data Analytical Technique

Descriptive and sediment quality indicators were applied to analyse the data using IBM statistical tool for social sciences version 22.0. Four sediment quality indicators namely; contamination factor (Cf),

pollution load index (PLI), potential contamination index (PCI) and geo-accumulation index (I-geo) were examined. The global Earth's shale values for metals, according to Turekian & Wedepohl (1961) was employed in this study as background value due to the lack of background record of metals in the bottom sediments of the study area (See Table 1).

Assessment of Sediment Quality Indicators

Contamination factor (Cf)

The contamination factor is an important index for determining the degree of anthropogenic heavy metal contamination in sediments. The index can be obtained by dividing the concentration of each metal in the sediments by the background value as stated in equation 1 (Hakanson, 1980; Bonnail, *et al.* 2016). The classification of Cf value were grouped into four namely; low contamination (Cf < 1), moderate contamination (1 < Cf < 3), considerable contamination (3 < Cf < 6), and very high contamination (Cf > 6) according to Bonnail, *et al.* (2016).

$$CF = Cs/Cref \dots \dots \dots (Eq.1)$$

Where Cs and Cref are concentrations of the element in the sediment sample and the background or pristine value of the element, respectively.

Pollution load index (PLI)

The PLI can be obtained as Cfs which represent the quotient obtained by dividing the concentration of each metal (Adel, *et al.* (2011). The evaluation of the index is based on the n-root from the n-CFs obtained from the heavy metals under investigation (Tomlinson, *et al.* 1980; Soares, *et al.* 1999; Adel, *et al.* 2011; Li, *et al.* 2013). The formula for the computation of the PLI is stated in equation 2. The PLI is grouped into two namely; polluted (PLI > 1) and no pollution (PLI <1) according to Harikumar, *et al.* (2009).

$$PLI = (Cf1 \times Cf2 \times Cf3 \times Cf4 \dots \dots Cfn)^{(1/n)}. (Eq. 2)$$

Potential contamination index (PCI)

The computation of PCI was determined according to Hakanson (1980) formula indicated in equation 3.

$$Cp = (Metal)Samplemaximum / (Metal)Background \dots \dots \dots (Eq. 3)$$

Where (Metal) Sample maximum is the maximum concentration of a metal in sediment, and (Metal) Background is the average value of the same metal in a background level. The PCI value was classified into three namely; Cp < 1 (low contamination), 1 < Cp < 3 (moderate contamination) and Cp > 3 (severe or very severe contamination according to Tomlinson, *et al.* (1980), Davaulter & Rognerud (2001) scheme.

Geo-accumulation index (I-geo)

The I-geo index represents a quantitative measure used in determining the extent of pollution in aquatic sediments by comparing its current concentrations with pre-industrial status (Muller, 1979). The computation of I-geo was determined using the formula proposed by Muller (1979) as indicated in equation 4.

$$Igeo = Log2[\frac{Cn}{1.5Bn}] \dots \dots \dots (Eq.4)$$

Where Cn is the measured concentration in the sediment for the metal n, Bn is the background value for the metal n), and 1.5 is a factor that represents the lithological variations of the background data (Turekian & Wedepohl, 1961). The I-geo index value was classified into seven groups namely; Igeo < 0 (uncontaminated), 0 ≤ Igeo < 1 (uncontaminated to moderately contaminated), 1 ≤ Igeo < 2 (moderately contaminated), 2 ≤ Igeo < 3 (moderately to heavily contaminated), 3 ≤ Igeo < 4 (heavily contaminated), 4 ≤ Igeo < 5 (heavily to extremely contaminated), 5 ≥ Igeo (extremely contaminated) (Müller, 1979; García, *et al.* 2008; Zalewska, *et al.* 2015).

Results and Discussion

Heavy Metal Concentration in Sediment

The concentrations of heavy metals in bottom sediments are in the order of: Cu > Mn > Pb > As > Cr > Zn > Ni > Hg > Co >

Cd. The descriptive statistics show that the mean value of Pb, Cd, As, Cu and Hg had concentrations values above the global background data while Zn, Mn, and Ni concentration were found to be below the global background data in the study area (Table 1).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of heavy metal in bottom sediment of River Ogun

Locations	Pb	Zn	Mn	Cr	Co	Cd	Ni	As	Cu	Hg
Kara	191.27	64.51	201.18	78.91	16.81	4.12	61.22	181.634	411.38	22.46
Magodo	161.67	31.23	187.02	70.45	12.84	2.96	36.45	138.64	286.71	23.12
Ketu	136.81	51.26	192.35	86.73	14.88	3.05	42.85	162.93	281.47	24.03
Mile12	186.77	71.38	216.78	72.42	18.98	4.37	57.35	192.46	261.49	26.12
Owode	122.48	35.91	181.07	61.35	11.81	2.48	22.68	116.85	81.48	18.92
Majidun	173.451	42.83	184.51	84.69	12.16	4.25	58.21	148.32	306.45	20.40
Itowolo	158.91	41.39	180.06	80.41	12.46	3.27	52.89	141.08	311.48	21.92
Olowora	175.12	68.44	221.67	91.11	19.06	6.08	41.31	176.09	345.28	21.71
Agboyi	180.40	70.91	204.52	84.08	18.78	4.87	38.45	184.30	482.36	26.71
Ogudu	211.68	73.46	230.17	91.27	19.12	6.71	62.15	192.46	618.05	31.11
Mean	169.86	55.13	199.93	80.14	15.69	4.22	47.35	163.48	338.62	23.65
Max	211.68	73.46	230.17	91.27	19.12	6.71	62.15	192.46	618.05	31.11
Min	122.48	31.23	180.06	61.35	11.81	2.48	22.68	116.85	81.48	18.92
Background value	20	95	850	90	19	0.3	68	13	45	0.4

NB: Max- maximum, Min-minimum, Unit of measurement - Kg⁻¹

Source: Author's (2019)

Regarding Cr and Co, 20% each, had concentrations above the global background data with approximately 40 and 30% of the locations having their concentrations above the mean value respectively. Copper and Cd recorded the highest and lowest concentration at Ogudu and Owode respectively. Previous studies have shown that Cr is known to cause cancer of the lung, nasal cavity and paranasal sinus including cancer of the stomach and larynx (ATSDR, 2000). It is also responsible for low sperm count (Anglin-Brown, *et al.* 1995). A high concentration of Pb can damage the kidney, liver and nervous system (Sharma & Pervez, 2003). Elevated levels of Cu can cause anaemia, liver damage, stomach and intestinal irritation (Turnland, 1988). A high concentration of Cd can result in physiological effects such as decreased growth rates and poor embryonic development (Newman & McIntosh, 1991). The observed high concentrations of heavy metals in this site can be attributed to high

anthropogenic activities around the area. A similar study by Akan, *et al.* (2010) reported similar findings. Ogudu had the highest concentrations value for all the heavy metals while Owode recorded the lowest concentrations values for all the heavy metals except for Zn and Mn. The high levels of Pb and Zn in the area can be linked to indiscriminate solid waste disposal. Previous studies by Akan *et al.* (2010), Wogu & Okaka (2011), Aladesanmi *et al.* (2016) and Ayoade & Nathaniel (2018) on heavy metal contamination in river sediment are in agreement with the present result. High concentrations of heavy metals in bottom sediments can disrupt the food chain leading to environmental and health challenges (Eja, *et al.* 2003; Chukwujindu, *et al.* 2007).

Contamination factor and pollution load index

The Cfs of Pb, As, Cd and Hg indicate very high contamination while the Cfs of Zn, Mn, Cr, Co, Cu and Ni are indicative of low contamination (See Table 2

and Fig.2). This result aligns with the findings of Puyate et al. (2007). The patterns of sediment contamination based on Cfs

shows that locations 8 & 10 have moderate contamination based on Cr and Co and location 5 based on Cu (Figures 2a-c).

Figure 2a: Contamination factor of Chromium in River Ogun

Figure 2b: Contamination factor of Cobalt in River Ogun

Figure 2c: Contamination factor of Copper in River Ogun

The computed Cf of Hg shows that it has the highest value of 77.78 while Mn has the lowest. Ogudu has the highest Cfs for all the observed metal concentrations. The observed high concentrations of metals at Ogudu can be linked with the level of human activities such as mechanic workshops etc. and its connection with the

Lagos lagoon while Owode recorded the lowest except for Zn which have the lowest value at Magodo. The result of the PLI varied from 1.68 to 3.52 with a mean value of 2.66 mg kg⁻¹ (Table 2). The computed PLI indicate that all the locations are polluted with Ogudu recording the highest PLI while Owode has the lowest value. This result contradicts the findings of Adel, et al. (2011).

Table 2: Contamination factors and Pollution load index of heavy metals in bottom sediment of River Ogun

S/No	Location	Contamination factors of heavy metals							PLI
		Pb	Zn	Mn	Cd	Ni	As	Hg	
1	Kara	9.56	0.68	0.24	13.73	0.90	13.97	56.15	3.18
2	Magodo	8.08	0.33	0.22	9.87	0.54	10.66	57.80	2.19
3	Ketu	6.84	0.54	0.23	10.17	0.63	12.53	60.08	2.44
4	Mile ₁₂	9.34	0.75	0.26	14.57	0.84	14.80	65.30	2.88
5	Owode	6.12	0.38	0.21	8.27	0.33	8.99	47.30	1.68
6	Majidun	8.67	0.45	0.22	14.17	0.86	11.41	51.00	2.51
7	Itowolo	7.95	0.44	0.21	10.90	0.78	10.85	54.80	2.39
8	Olowora	8.76	0.72	0.26	20.27	0.61	13.55	54.28	2.93
9	Agboyi	9.02	0.75	0.24	16.23	0.00	14.18	66.78	2.98
10	Ogudu	10.58	0.77	0.27	22.37	0.91	14.80	77.78	3.52
interpretation		VHC	LC	LC	VHC	LC	VHC	VHC	Polluted
	Min	6.12	0.33	0.21	8.27	0.00	8.99	47.30	1.68
	Max	10.58	0.77	0.27	22.37	0.91	14.80	77.78	3.52
	Mean	8.47	0.58	0.24	14.26	0.61	12.46	59.69	2.66

NB: VHC-Very high contamination, LC: low contamination

The result of the PCI of the bottom sediment of River Ogun shows that it ranged from 0.27 to 77.8. (Table 3). The PCI indicate that 50% of the metals in the study area mainly from Pb, Cd, As, Cu and Hg indicate very severe PCI. Similarly, 30% of the metals from Zn,

Mn and Ni are indicative of moderate PCI while 20% from Cr and Co represent low PCI in the study area (See fig. 3). Mercury recorded the highest PCI while Mn has the lowest in the study area.

Figure 3: Patterns of PCI in bottom sediment of River Ogun

The computed I-geo shows that Pb is uncontaminated (Table 4). Similarly, Zn indicates uncontaminated. However, location 2 shows moderate contamination as indicated in Figure 4a. The observed low I-geo values of Pb and Zn indicates that the concentrations of the metal result from the natural weathering process (Achi, *et al.* 2020). Chromium, As and Cu are characterised by low contamination while

Hg is of moderate contamination (Table 4). Approximately 40, 40 and 20% of the locations show heavy, moderate to heavy contamination and moderate contamination for Mn respectively (Fig. 4b). About 90 and 10% of the locations based on the computed I-geo for Ni indicate low and moderate contamination respectively as shown in Figure 4c. Similarly, 70 and 30% of the sites are indicative of low and extreme contamination based on Cd in the study area (Fig. 4d).

Table 4. Geo-accumulation index of heavy metals in bottom sediment of River Ogun

S/N	I-geo Pb	I-geo Cr	I-geo Co	I-geo As	I-geo Cu	I-geo Hg
1	-2.56	0.11	0.11	-21.45	-2.25	2.41
2	-1.62	0.15	0.23	-3.68	-0.94	2.38
3	-1.10	0.08	0.15	-7.87	-0.90	2.36
4	-2.39	0.14	0.07	-120.50	-0.77	2.30
5	-0.86	0.22	0.28	-2.14	-0.02	2.57
6	-1.94	0.09	0.26	-4.83	-1.08	2.49

7	-1.55	0.10	0.24	-3.93	-1.12	2.43
8	-1.99	0.07	0.07	-14.63	-1.43	2.43
9	-2.16	0.09	0.07	-27.26	-3.75	2.29
10	-3.58	0.07	0.07	-120.50	-17.08	2.20
Min	-3.58	0.07	0.07	-120.50	-17.08	2.20
Max	-0.86	0.22	0.28	-2.14	-0.02	2.57

Figure 4a: Geo-accumulation index of Zinc in River Ogun

Figure 4b: Geo-accumulation index of Manganese in River Ogun

Figure 4c: Geo-accumulation index of Nickel in River Ogun

Figure 4d: Geo-accumulation index of Cadmium in River Ogun

Conclusion

The present study analyzed the patterns of bottom sediment contamination in parts of River Ogun Lagos, Nigeria using contamination factor, pollution load index, potential contamination index and geo-accumulation index. The findings shows that the concentrations of heavy metals in bottom sediments are in the order of: Cu >

Mn > Pb > As > Cr > Zn > Ni > Hg > Co > Cd. The concentrations of Pb, Cd, As, Cu and Hg were found to be above the global background values in the bottom sediment of the study area. Ogudu recorded the highest concentrations value in all the heavy metals in bottom sediment while Owode recorded the lowest except for Zn and Mn in the study area. The computed contamination factors revealed that Pb, As, Cd and Hg indicate very

high contamination. The computed PLI shows that all the locations are polluted based on the heavy metals examined. The computed pollution contamination index shows that half of the examined locations indicate very severe contamination due to the contributions from Pb, Cd, As, Cu and Hg. Mercury recorded the highest Cf and PCI values in the study area. The computed I-geo of Pb and Zn show no contamination while Cr, Ni As and Cu indicate low contamination. About 40% of the locations indicate heavy contamination based on I-geo of Mn while 30% of the sites are extremely contaminated based on Cd. The study concluded that Ogudu recorded the worst site having the highest concentrations value for all the heavy metals, Cf, and PLI while Owode has the least pollution in the study area. The study is significant because it provides useful baseline information on the overall level of heavy metal concentrations and ecological risk of heavy metal contamination in bottom sediments of the study area for efficient monitoring and regulation of potential environmental and health challenges for informed policy decisions. The study suggested appropriate monitoring of effluents at Ogudu to control the possible sediment degradation entering the Lagos Lagoon from the area. Enforcement of regulatory standards of pollution abatement in the aquatic environment was also proffered.

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